

TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE WITH THE MEANS OF MOODLE PLATFORM

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Abstract. This article is focused to using the Moodle online learning platform. Consideration is given to the Moodle system's features and benefits. The elements of distant learning focused on enhancing listening, writing, and reading abilities in teaching English are given special consideration. In the article, assignments for solitary, couple, and group work in English lessons are illustrated. In conclusion, it is determined that remote learning is beneficial because it allows students to acquire and control their own information and transforms the teacher's position from that of a translator to that of a tutor.

Keywords: methodology, English language, language teaching, moodle, IT, interactive learning, method, moodle platform.

ОБУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СРЕДСТВАМИ ПЛАТФОРМЫ MOODLE

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена использованию платформы онлайн-обучения Moodle. Рассмотрены возможности и преимущества системы Moodle. Особое внимание уделяется элементам дистанционного обучения, направленным на улучшение навыков аудирования, письма и чтения при обучении английскому языку. В статье проиллюстрированы задания для одиночной, парной и групповой работы на уроках английского языка. В заключение определено, что дистанционное обучение выгодно, поскольку оно позволяет учащимся получать и контролировать собственную информацию и трансформирует позицию учителя из позиции переводчика в позицию репетитора.

Ключевые слова: методика, английский язык, обучение языку, мудл, информационные технологии, интерактивное обучение, метод, мудл-платформа.

INTRODUCTION

One of the sectors of the educational system with the quickest growth, both domestically and abroad, is distance education. The biggest educational and communication firms are presently creating courses for students and schoolchildren to learn from home in a variety of subjects. The design of courses in the humanities or natural sciences is not advised, although there are technological options and a minimal basic set of needs for the framework. There are psychological and pedagogical suggestions for course design in contemporary scientific literature. It is feasible to develop a system of methodological guidelines for the development of distant learning courses on the basis of current student training programs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of online courses in the remote education system (LMS) LMS MOODLE is one of the areas for implementing e-learning at the Uzbek State University of World Languages. This system's capability includes the following and contains a wealth of knowledge control tools:

- automated control of test outcomes (the instructor may allow pupils to examine their own test results or prevent them from being displayed by utilizing certain test-creation settings);

- the ability to evaluate and correct completed tasks, exercises, abstracts, essays, and projects (the teacher can, when evaluating independent work, provide the student with comments and comments on each of the answers for a clear understanding of the evaluation criteria);
- the ability to provide quick feedback (the results of the assessment of the completed independent work are provided to the teacher and student immediately after the test);
- the capability to report on the quantity and quality of completed assignments.
- the teacher's power to select and design a unique evaluation system for each work.

RESULTS

The Moodle platform enables instructors to design customized online courses for their students. It has the power to improve how well pupils are trained in a certain field. The benefit of Moodle is that it does not need the instructor to have any prior expertise of website development, database management, programming, etc. Any instructor may use this system to learn how to plan, construct, and manage the learning and control process on an intuitive level.

The instructor can independently construct an electronic course and manage its work with the aid of the suggestions and assistance provided by the support system. The Moodle system is made to support any multimedia resources required for the creation of new ones, the improvement of current ones, or the verification of learned information (video and audio material, tables, diagrams, etc.). The customization feature enables the instructor to quickly and easily choose the color scheme and other design elements of the teaching material, even without having any prior understanding of HTML.

The course structure may be chosen in any way that the instructor deems appropriate. The course might be organized thematically or chronologically. Students can study instructional content with a specific subject within the suggested portions when it is organized thematically. The weekly course being studied may be found via calendar structure, and the student can individually organize their time for its completion. The employed electronic resources could include both information resources and tools for evaluating student work (assignments, tests, lectures, etc.).

In the higher education system, lectures receive a lot of attention. The essential components of the Lecture course using Moodle can be built. The competent design of this component, which serves as the foundation of the entire course, will enhance and diversify the learning experience. The "lecture" is structured so that there are transitions that are required from one section of the lesson to the next.

The solution enables the creator of the educational course to alter the content and make changes while the trainees are still receiving training. The instructor has the authority to alter the components' order and, if required, add lectures, glossaries, discussions, and other activities. The Moodle system enables instructors to display their training course materials, lead theoretical and practical classes, and plan solo, pair, and group work owing to the expanded features. The most typical sort of individual job is test performance, which involves selecting the one and only true response from the available options. The Moodle platform offers a variety of opportunities for students to complete individual activities and assess if their responses are true or false (True/False activity).

After completing a task, the creator of the online educational course has the option of giving the students a summary of the assessment that lists the total number of participants, the

minimum number of replies, and the real points earned. When working in pairs, a particular discussion topic and set of questions are suggested. For instance, when faced with the challenge of starting a blog, students respond to the following questions:

- Why do you want to start a blog?
- What kind of media, such as text, images, videos, and audio files, would you put on your blog?

Students also have the chance to provide a new debate topic and to voice their opinions. It is advised to conclude the educational program with a final control block, which might take the form of an exam, test, final work, or test. The primary concerns while developing such courses are the efficiency and efficacy of e-introduction learning's for both the teacher and the student.

DISCUSSION

Experts agree that students' motivation, activity, and attention stability are issues with distant learning. It is crucial to consider the potential for one-on-one contact (in the classroom), synchronous and asynchronous (remote format), and the suitable selection of various LMS modules.

It is not sufficient to add distant learning to the classroom on a sporadic basis in order to arrange remote classroom instruction. To have a synergistic impact, full-time and distant education must come together inseparably.

The Moodle system's English language course should be comprehensive, and the system itself should let students to take tests of their foundational abilities in listening, writing, and reading (listening, writing, reading). All of these abilities may be developed through distant learning.

It is easy to include an audio or video clip on one page and include questions (a test) on the content heard in order to build listening skills. You can condense the time given for replies by modifying.

It is recommended to provide pupils writing tasks in the form of essays, which can be turned in as texts or files attached. You may utilize multiple-choice exam questions on many writing-related themes to build the coherence and logic of producing a particular assertion.

It is ideal for pupils to supply the appropriate material and assignments for it in order to enhance reading abilities. It is sufficient to link to the text; it is not necessary to post it. You may give a lecture on the website and provide tasks for it. Students get the knowledge they need from the suggested lecture and respond to the suggested questions. The learner may move on to the following page if the response is accurate. It is vital to review the given information if the page transition does not occur.

Along with the skills suggested, this environment can expand vocabulary by creating activities for matching, such as word-to-word, sentence-to-sentence, picture-to-sentence, etc.; testing for lexical units; and employing the produced tasks.

CONCLUSIONS

With the help of Moodle, teachers may do analysis without devoting a lot of time to it while students can gain and regulate their own information. Distance learning is more efficient, as evidenced by the current issues with it. With such instruction, the teacher's function shifts from that of a translator to that of a tutor.

The instructor encourages and reorganizes the educational process rather than merely transferring pre-made information. Even now, it is possible to analyze and draw conclusions

about the effectiveness of the distance course in terms of compliance with the methodological, psychological, and pedagogical principles of organizing training, as well as conclusions about the level of attendance. These are questions of psychological and pedagogical research in the coming decades.

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